

Risk and Ownership Structure: Analyzing Residential Property Values in Broward County, 2022-2023

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ABSTRACT

Climate-related hazards, such as floods, threaten housing markets and infrastructure globally. This study explores the intricate relationship between flood risk, property values, and corporate ownership. The interplay of these factors is critical for individual property owners and broader economic stability and urban planning. Key questions include: Is there a relationship between flood risk and appraised property value? Is there a relationship between corporate ownership and appraised property value? Does an interaction between flood risk and corporate ownership affect the average appraised property value? Is there a meaningful difference in these relationships and interactions between 2022 and 2023? Using a hedonic pricing analysis and 2022 and 2023 Broward County, Florida property data from the Broward County Appraiser's Office, the study determined an associated *decrease* of approximately 5.5% in 2022 and 5.1% in 2023 in the property value of high flood-risk properties. The analysis also determined that for properties owned by a corporate entity, there was an associated *decrease* of approximately 3.6% in 2022 and 3.1% in 2023 in the property value, indicating that holding other variables constant, corporate-owned properties are typically associated with lower values. Finally, there was an associated *increase* of approximately 10.2% in 2022 and 9.6% in 2023 in property values for properties that are *both* high flood risk and owned by a corporate entity. This indicates that, controlling for the other variables in the model, high flood-risk properties owned by a business appear to have appreciably *higher* property values on average.

Keywords: Flood risk, property values, corporate ownership, hedonic pricing analysis, real estate

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the escalating threats posed by climate change have become a focal point for academic, economic, and policy discussions worldwide. Among the myriad challenges this global phenomenon presents, the increasing frequency and severity of flooding stand out as a particularly urgent issue. From 1980 to April 2024, the US experienced 44 billion-dollar flooding events that cost an average of \$4.4 billion in annual damages (about \$4.5 billion per event) and 16 deaths yearly (NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information, 2024). First Street Foundation's research reveals that around 4.3 million residential homes in the U.S. face significant annual flood risks, potentially causing economic damages of about \$20 billion annually and projected to increase by 61% to \$32.2 billion within 30 years due to climate change impacts (First Street Foundation, 2021). Current National Flood Insurance Program rates would need to quintuple to adequately cover these risks, highlighting a nationwide underestimation of flood-related economic losses (First Street Foundation, 2021).

Approximately 40% of the U.S. population resides in coastal areas, with Florida being one of the top five states by coastal population size (NOAA, 2024). Analysis shows that at least \$108 billion of assessed value in the U.S. is at risk from rising seas by 2100, affecting property tax revenues, which can greatly impact community welfare (Climate Central, 2022). Property taxes are one of the only revenue sources that municipalities control and account for an average of 30% of local revenues, with 64 Florida municipalities collecting 50% of their revenues from high flood-risk zoned properties (Diezmartínez & Short Gianotti, 2024). The risks, however, might not be evenly distributed, as findings show that the municipalities with the highest risks are typically dense, wealthy, and white. In contrast, lower-risk municipalities generally are lower income, diverse, more populous, and have larger land areas (Diezmartínez & Short Gianotti, 2024).

Regarding property value, it is logical to consider whether flood risk is priced into the property's value, as typically, all financial assets in a perfect market would price in their inherent risks. Generally, as in Florida, highly-priced residential properties lie along the coast in typically high flood-risk zones (CoreLogic, 2023). There are often no flood risk disclosure laws and little discussion about flood risk when buyers evaluate fair market prices for prospective properties (Caraballo, 2024). On June 22, 2024, Florida Governor Ron DeSantis signed HB 1049 into law,

mandating sellers to disclose significant flood risk details and past insurance claims related to flood damage to homebuyers, with the legislation set to take effect on October 1, 2024, marking a step towards greater transparency in real estate transactions (Environmental Defense Fund, 2024).

Past research has been split on whether flood risk depresses property values or is correlated with an overvaluation, ranging from a 75.5% decrease to a 61.0% increase in value (Beltrán et al., 2018). For instance, Bin and Polasky (2004) found that homes at higher risk of flooding sell at noticeably lower prices, reflecting the increased cost of insurance and potential damage (Bin & Polasky, 2004). Another study agreed with the assessment that properties located within flood zones typically exhibit a reduction in value, as evidenced by the study's regression analyses, which found high flood-risk coastal property discounts of 18% (He, 2022). Under severe climate scenarios, including a high-emissions climate risk model, CoreLogic's study "The impact of flood risk on property values – a case study in Miami" found that coastal properties could experience significant devaluation due to increased flood risks, projecting that heightened sea levels and increased frequency and severity of flooding could lead to substantial property value losses, estimated at billions of dollars in high-risk areas like Miami (He, 2022).

In contrast, other studies show an overvaluation in flood risk properties. For example, residential properties in flood-prone areas were shown to be overvalued by \$121 to \$237 billion, mainly in coastal counties lacking flood risk disclosure laws and where climate change concern is low (Gourevitch et al., 2023). This overvaluation poses significant risks to low-income homeowners and tax-reliant municipalities, with future financial impacts dependent on climate policy decisions. An earlier study found that housing markets do not fully price in the risks indicated by floodplain maps, leading to an overvaluation of properties in flood zones by an estimated \$43.8 billion (Hino & Burke, 2021). Authors Hino and Burke further highlighted that more informed buyers, such as commercial purchasers or those in states with strict disclosure laws, tend to discount property values more in flood-prone areas, suggesting that improving risk communication could enhance market efficiency (2021).

A lack of accountable information, interest, or knowledge in incorporating risk information in property purchase decisions may influence the inaccurate property valuations of high flood-risk properties. Do property values accurately incorporate flood risk, accounting for all present and future risks? Hino and Burke (2021) examined how well flood risks are integrated into property

values across the U.S., using data from millions of home sales and regulatory floodplain maps. They found that the housing market does not fully incorporate flood risk information into property values. This underpricing of flood risks is more pronounced where buyers are less informed or where flood risk communication is weaker, encouraging potentially risky property development in flood-prone areas. Shu et al. found that Special Flood Hazard Area (SFHA) designations, perceived as flood risk indicators, influence property values in Miami-Dade County, separate from actual flood risk, due to changes in insurance costs and buyer perceptions (2022). The study controlled for actual flood risks to assess SFHA impacts independently. It noted that properties moving into SFHA zones experience valuation losses while those moving out see gains.

Perhaps only savvy institutional or investor-like buyers look for a risk discount in flood-risk properties (Khater, Kiefer, & Atreya, 2020). Although FEMA publishes flood risk zones for individual residential properties online at no cost, it is unclear which buyers consider flood risk in their purchase decisions, whether it is considered by all buyers or only investment-savvy buyers (Dunsavage, 2022). Misclassifying high-risk homes for low-risk homes in terms of flooding creates an overvaluation and overleverage (Gourevitch et al., 2023). Large property-holding companies often possess the resources to implement extensive flood mitigation measures, potentially offsetting some of the negative impacts of flood risk on property values (Lamond et al., 2017). Similarly, commercial real estate investors were shown to assess a larger price discount to properties damaged by hurricanes in response to a more significant climate awareness and a more spatially diverse portfolio (Holdermans, 2023). Given more accurate information, savvy owners might also monopolize valuable real estate, exacerbating economic disparities and profoundly influencing local markets (Logan & Molotch, 1987).

Furthermore, a nationwide natural field experiment conducted through Redfin assessed the impact of providing home-specific flood risk information on home buyers' behavior. The study found that flood risk information significantly influenced every stage of the home-buying process, including search, bidding, and purchasing decisions (Katz, Fairweather, and Sandoval-Olascoaga, 2022). Buyers were willing to trade off property amenities for lower flood risk, especially in high-risk areas. This information led to changes in property prices and market equilibrium, affecting approximately \$135 billion of real estate, highlighting the importance of climate adaptation in real estate decisions (Fairweather et al., 2023).

Understanding the property flood risk dynamics becomes increasingly critical, especially in low-lying regions like Broward County, Florida which are prone to coastal and inland flooding, especially with rising sea levels and more intense storms due to climate change. The region's location makes it more susceptible to storm surges, heavy rainfall, and tidal flooding, complicating flood risk assessments. By examining the effects of flood risk on property values and the role of different types of ownership, this paper seeks to add valuable insights to the ongoing discourse. Broward County had two “billion-dollar flooding disaster events” in 2023, totaling over \$1.4 billion in CPI-adjusted costs (NOAA, 2024). This study hypothesized that high flood-risk properties would have higher property values due to a lack of knowledge about flood risk by the average homeowner and that investor-owned properties would have lower flood risk and lower values as compared with individually owned properties due to their savvier ability to appropriately value risk. Through a detailed analysis of recent data, particularly in light of the significant flooding events in 2023, this study aims to provide evidence that could guide more informed policy decisions and strategic planning, ultimately contributing to the resilience and stability of real estate markets in the face of escalating climate threats.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Aim of the Study

This study aims to analyze the effects of flood risk and type of ownership (individual vs. corporate) on residential property values in Broward County, Florida for 2022 and 2023.

2.2. Source of the Data

Data is from the Broward County, Florida Appraiser’s Office (2022 and 2023), received in a .xlsx (Excel) file with 755,326 rows of data with each row generally affiliated with one property, and a key to the column names. Unnecessary column data, such as “Last Year’s Save Our Home Land Value,” “Last Year’s Save Our Home Building Value,” “Widows Veterans Disability Amount,” “School Board Mixed Exemption Amount,” etc., that were not included in our analysis were deleted. Specific property variables (column data) that were included in the analysis included the following:

1. Identification of the properties, such as FOLIO_NUMBER.

2. Geographical data, such as ADDRESS_LINE_1, CITY, STATE, ZIP.
3. Appraised value of properties, including JUST_LAND_VALUE + JUST_BUILDING_VALUE, since the appraised value equals land value plus building value.
4. FEMA codes to evaluate flood risk as high or low. Although properties may have more than one FEMA code associated with them, with a different flood-prone zone on the same property, since the data set from the Tax Collector's office in Broward County, Florida, had only one specified zone, the one used in the analysis. FLD_ZONE, the column for the FEMA zone, was used to create a high/low flood risk variable. The rows with FLD_ZONE== AH, AE, VE, and AO were coded as IS_HIGH_FLD_RISK==1 (high flood risk), while those with FLD_ZONE==X were coded as IS_HIGH_FLD_RISK==0 (low flood risk).
5. Property differences that we set control (e.g., amenities, size, age, location, etc.) included BLDG_ADJ_SQ_FOOTAGE, square footage; BLDG_YEAR_BUILT year built; BLDG_CCLAS, class of building; BEDS, number of bedrooms; BATHS, number of bathrooms; and SITUS_CITY, city name.
6. Type of owner is either "mom-and-pop"/individual/family buyer or business/corporate.

Duplicate or incomplete entries for key predictor variables were deleted, resulting in a data file with 707,749 properties.

2.3. Description of Independent and Dependent Variables

The important contributing independent variables to the property's appraised value (dependent variable) were determined to be the following: BLDG_ADJ_SQ_FOOTAGE, square footage; BLDG_YEAR_BUILT, year built; BLDG_CCLAS, class of building; BEDS, number of bedrooms; BATHS, number of bathrooms; SITUS_CITY, city name; IS_HIGH_FLD_RISK, high flood risk or not; IS_BUSINESS, owned by corporation/"business" or not. The two variables of interest, whether the property was in a high flood risk zone "FLD_ZONE" or not, and whether the property was owned by an individual/homeowner or a corporate entity "IS_BUSINESS," were coded as binary variables. "FLD_ZONE" of 1 equated to a high flood risk property and "FLD_ZONE" of FALSE equated to a non-high-flood risk property. "IS_BUSINESS" of FALSE equated to an individual owner and "IS_BUSINESS" of TRUE

equated to a corporate entity owner. Establishing individual versus corporate/business ownership was challenging. As the Broward County Appraiser's Office analyst recommended, we looked at how ownership names were listed in columns; individuals reliably had first and last names separated by a comma in the format LASTNAME, FIRSTNAME with a comma delineating, while the corporate owners did not have a comma anywhere in the NAME. A more sophisticated approach might use modern text and natural language processing to identify which names indicated businesses.

These variables are well-known determinants of property value. Each factor contributes to the overall market price, with more bedrooms and bathrooms typically increasing the value, while larger square footage and acreage also add to a property's worth. City codes often serve as proxies for location-specific factors such as neighborhood quality, school districts, and proximity to amenities. Including city codes in the analysis helps capture these location-based variations in property value, which are critical in real estate pricing. Some of these variables may be correlated (e.g., larger properties might have more bedrooms and bathrooms). Regression analysis can help identify and adjust for multicollinearity, ensuring that the unique contribution of each variable to property value is accurately assessed. Homebuyers often face trade-offs, such as choosing between more bedrooms or larger acreage within the same budget. Regression analysis helps in understanding these trade-offs, offering insights into how different combinations of features affect the overall price. The analysis can provide insights into buyer behavior and preferences. For instance, if the number of bathrooms has a stronger effect on property value than the number of bedrooms, it could indicate a shift in consumer priorities that developers and investors need to consider.

2.4. Methodology

An ordinary least squares (OLS) regression analysis with variables such as the number of bedrooms, bathrooms, square footage, and zip code was used as it is academically viable for several reasons. Regression analysis is a typical method used to analyze real estate property values. Variables often include property structural variables like size, age of property, and amenities; locational variables like proximity to important institutions; market variables like interest rates and unemployment rates; environmental variables like flood risk and proximity to bodies of water; and regulatory variables like zoning and tax policies. Beltrán et al. used

meta-regression analysis to examine how flood risk is capitalized into property values (2018) and Bin & Polasky (2004) employed ordinary least squares (OLS) regression to determine the impact of flood risk on house prices before and after Hurricane Floyd (2004).

The outcome variable of our regression model was the property appraised value PROP_VAL. To investigate whether this choice was sensible, the histogram of the outcome variable was examined, which was very positively skewed. Therefore, a natural logarithm transformation was needed to make it less skewed, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Histogram of Logarithm of 2022-2023 Property Values

This normal distribution indicated that a better outcome choice would be the appraised value log. The current model studied the linear relationship between the variables and the logarithm of the appraised value $\log(\text{PROP_VAL})$, which was conducted using R software.

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\text{PROP_VAL}) = & \beta_0 \\ & + \beta_1 * \text{BLDG_ADJ_SQ_FOOTAGE} \\ & + \beta_2 * \text{ACTUAL_YEAR_BUILT} \\ & + \beta_3 * \text{BLDG_CCLAS} \\ & + \beta_4 * \text{BEDS} \\ & + \beta_5 * \text{BATHS} \\ & + \beta_6 * \text{SITUS_CITY_CS} \\ & + \vdots \\ & + \beta_{36} * \text{SITUS_CITY_LZ} \\ & + \beta_{37} * \text{IS_HIGH_FLD_RISK} \\ & + \beta_{38} * \text{IS_BUSINESS} \\ & + \beta_{39} * \text{IS_HIGH_FLD_RISK} * \text{IS_BUSINESS} \\ & + \epsilon \end{aligned}$$

Where:

- $\beta_p, p = 0, \dots, 39$ are the regression coefficients
- ϵ is the error term.

Note that the terms $\beta_6 * \text{SITUS_CITY_CS} + \dots + \beta_{36} * \text{SITUS_CITY_LZ}$ terms correspond to the indicator variables for the various city codes and $\beta_p = 7, \dots, 35$ have been omitted for readability.

Diagnostic plots of the 2022 model indicated that the data fit the model well but that there were several outliers, as shown in Figure 2. In the Residuals vs Fitted graph, we see that the variance of the residuals are not evenly scattered across all levels of the independent variables.

Figure 2. Diagnostic Plots of 2022 Model

Moreover, the trend is for the residuals to become more and more negative as the property values get larger, indicating the model is systematically underestimating properties for which it is predicting the highest value, and that this gets worse as the property value grows. We note also that there are two observations with $\text{LOGPROPVALUE} \leq 0$ which have very high residuals. This plot indicates a violation of the linearity and constant variance assumptions. In the normal Q-Q Plot, there is reasonably good alignment along the 45-degree line, except for at the endpoints. By comparison with the Residuals vs Fitted plot, we notice the same problematic observations. The Scale-Location plot's funnel shape shows a violation of the homoscedasticity with the same problematic outlier points. Finally, the Residuals vs Leverage Plot shows 5 points outside Cook's outermost distance contour.

Additionally, the multiple and adjusted R-squared values for both 2022 and 2023 were low, with an adjusted R-squared value for 2023 of 0.2737, indicating an estimated 27.37% of the observed variance in property values accounted for by our regression model. Given the outliers and R-squared values, properties with fitted (predicted) log property values less than 10 and greater than 30 were removed, essentially restricting the analysis to properties with values between \$22,000 and \$10,000,000. This resulted in an improvement of about 5% in multiple and adjusted R-squared values for both 2022 and 2023 models.

3. RESULTS

The results presented below summarize the findings that properties in high flood-risk areas experienced a decrease in value of approximately 5.5% in 2022 and 5.3% in 2023, while corporate-owned properties saw a decrease of around 9-10%. However, properties that were both high flood-risk and corporate-owned saw an increase in value of about 11-13%.

Table 1. Property Category Percentages*

High Flood Risk	Corporate Owned	Number of Properties	Percentage of Properties
FALSE	FALSE	465,000	83.4%
FALSE	TRUE	92,567	16.6%

TRUE	FALSE	114,633	76.3%
TRUE	TRUE	35,549	23.7%

* Based on data after cleaning and before adjusting for goodness of fit. Identical for 2022 and 2023.

Figure 3. Percentage of Properties Owned By Business/Individual in High Flood Risk Zone* * Based on data after cleaning and before adjusting for goodness of fit. Identical for 2022 and 2023.

Table 1 and Figure 3 show that for properties in high flood-risk areas, 76.3% are individually owned and 23.7% are corporate-owned. In contrast, for properties in low flood-risk areas, 83.4% are individually owned and 16.6% are corporate-owned.

Our thesis was that individuals might own a greater number of high flood-risk properties because perhaps they would not consider flood risk in their decision to own a property with a potential for flood damage. However, the data showed that businesses own a greater percentage of high-risk properties than individuals do. Businesses view high-risk properties as investment opportunities and they price in the cost of flood insurance or recovery costs, but individual homeowners may not manage financial risks as well so they are less willing to absorb that risk (Hino & Burke, 2021). Since housing is local and some are regulated with flood disclosure laws while others are not, different communities weigh flooding risk and the positive amenities of being close to water differently (He, 2022).

Figure 4 shows that the Broward County cities with the greatest number of flood-risk properties are Tamarac, Davie, Plantation, Parkland, Pembroke Pines, Coral Springs, Lauderdale by the Sea, North Lauderdale, Coconut Creek, and Lauderdale Lakes. These cities are mostly located inland, as seen on the adjacent map. Furthermore, Figure 5 and Figure 6 show that Broward County zip codes in the high flood-risk zones are Hallandale, Hollywood, Pompano Beach, Deerfield Beach, Parkland, Coral Springs, Fort Lauderdale, and Tamarac. Interestingly, not all of these cities or zip codes are coastal, most are inland. This could be the result of infrastructure that is not designed to handle large quantities of rain, including impervious surfaces like roads and buildings that prevent water from being absorbed into the ground or drainage systems and waterways which may overflow when rainfall patterns are unusually high or unpredictable (South Florida Water Management, 2024).

Figure 4. Top Ten Broward County Cities By Percentage of High Flood-Risk Properties

Figure 5. Top Ten Broward County Zip Codes By Percentage of High Flood-Risk Properties

Figure 6. Broward County Zip Codes Map

(<https://adlerrp.weebly.com/broward-zip-code-map.html>.)

Fisher's exact test of variables IS_HIGH_FLD_RISK (property is in a FEMA high flood risk zone) and IS_BUSINESS (property is owned by a corporate entity, not an individual) resulted in p-value 0.0005, indicating that these two variables are statistically dependent. This result suggests strong statistical evidence that whether a property is business-owned tells us whether it is a high flood-risk property and vice versa. The two-way ANOVA test was used to analyze the interactions between flood risk (IS_HIGH_FLD_RISK), business ownership (IS_BUSINESS), and their combined effects on property values (PROP_VALUE). The resulting p-values of these relationships ($4.2426e^{-53}$, 0, and $1.7800e^{-10}$, respectively) indicate that property values individually are statistically dependent on whether that property has high flood risk or is business owned and also is statistically dependent on the interaction of these two. Flood risk and business ownership each have a significant association with property values, and the relationship between flood risk and property values depends on whether the property is business-owned (and vice versa).

While the multiple and adjusted R-squared values diagnostics improved slightly for both 2022 and 2023 by around 5%, as seen in Figure 7 and Figure 8, there is still an indication of poor agreement with the underlying linear regression assumptions. Figures 7 and 8 (2022 and 2023 models, respectively) display similar diagnostic issues. The Residuals vs Fitted plots indicate non-linearity, suggesting the models do not fully capture the relationship between variables. The Q-Q plots show deviations from normality in the residuals, violating the assumption that errors are normally distributed. Both Scale-Location plots reveal heteroscedasticity, with non-constant variance across the fitted values, while the Residuals vs Leverage plots suggest the presence of influential outliers that may be skewing the model's results. Overall, these diagnostics indicate that further refinement, such as adjusting for non-linearity or handling outliers, is necessary to improve the models.

Figure 8. Final Model Diagnostics for 2023

Table 2 Regression Model Coefficient Outputs and Statistical Results

Predictor Variable	2022 Coefficient Estimate	2022 % change*	p-value	2023 Coefficient Estimate	2023 % change*	p-value
Intercept	0.766927		0	-0.64154		0
BLDG_ADJ_SQ_FOOTAGE	0.000019	0.0%	0	0.000019	0.0%	0
ACTUAL_YEAR_BUILT	0.006695	0.7%	0	0.007488	0.8%	0
BLDG_CCLAS	0.182857	20.1%	0	0.190556	21.0%	0
BEDS	0.003996	0.4%	0	0.003732	0.4%	0
BATHS	0.076766	8.0%	0	0.075307	7.8%	0
SITUS_CITY_CS	-1.719774	-82.1%	0	-1.824218	-83.9%	0
SITUS_CITY_PA	-1.150425	-68.3%	0	-1.236559	-71.0%	0

SITUS_CITY_OP	-1.837356	-84.1%	0	-1.875961	-84.7%	0
SITUS_CITY_DV	-1.599555	-79.8%	0	-1.691251	-81.6%	0
SITUS_CITY_MM	-1.769505	-83.0%	0	-1.867152	-84.5%	0
SITUS_CITY_DN	-1.807819	-83.6%	0	-1.871185	-84.6%	0
SITUS_CITY_HA	-1.917007	-85.3%	0	-2.002461	-86.5%	0
SITUS_CITY_FL	-1.386456	-75.0%	0	-1.462388	-76.8%	0
SITUS_CITY_PI	-1.804738	-83.5%	0	-1.908612	-85.2%	0
SITUS_CITY_PB	-1.758732	-82.8%	0	-1.830926	-84.0%	0
SITUS_CITY_CY	-1.41216	-75.6%	0	-1.513188	-78.0%	0
SITUS_CITY_NL	-1.998903	-86.5%	0	-2.075276	-87.4%	0
SITUS_CITY_MG	-2.153163	-88.4%	0	-2.235444	-89.3%	0
SITUS_CITY_CK	-2.046613	-87.1%	0	-2.167576	-88.6%	0
SITUS_CITY_PK	-2.282751	-89.8%	0	-2.361423	-90.6%	0
SITUS_CITY_LL	-2.52993	-92.0%	0	-2.566807	-92.3%	0
SITUS_CITY_WM	-1.433542	-76.2%	0	-1.514456	-78.0%	0
SITUS_CITY_LS	-1.275381	-72.1%	0	-1.370819	-74.6%	0
SITUS_CITY_HW	-1.629626	-80.4%	0	-1.703414	-81.8%	0
SITUS_CITY_HB	-1.318702	-73.3%	0	-1.445305	-76.4%	0
SITUS_CITY_DB	-2.07049	-87.4%	0	-2.140223	-88.2%	0
SITUS_CITY_BC	-1.794393	-83.4%	0	-1.833955	-84.0%	0
SITUS_CITY_PL	-1.701824	-81.8%	0	-1.768745	-82.9%	0
SITUS_CITY_TM	-2.172748	-88.6%	0	-2.262145	-89.6%	0

SITUS_CITY_SW	-0.767395	-53.6%	0	-0.834876	-56.6%	0
SITUS_CITY_SU	-2.090241	-87.6%	0	-2.182859	-88.7%	0
SITUS_CITY_WP	-1.704959	-81.8%	0	-1.755025	-82.7%	0
SITUS_CITY_LH	-2.322117	-90.2%	0	-2.385302	-90.8%	0
SITUS_CITY_LP	-1.216823	-70.4%	0	-1.294009	-72.6%	0
SITUS_CITY_WS	-1.389736	-75.1%	0	-1.498725	-77.7%	0
SITUS_CITY_LZ	-0.973011	-62.2%	0	-0.054178	-5.3%	0
IS_HIGH_FLD_RISKTRUE	-0.057691	-5.6%	0	-0.054178	-5.3%	0
IS_BUSINESSTRUE	-0.095309	-9.1%	0	-0.092307	-8.8%	0
IS_HIGH_FLD_RISKTRUE:IS_BUSINESSTRUE	0.123317	13.1%	0	0.109377	11.6%	0

*% change refers to the percentage change in the property value caused by the listed predictor variable, controlling for all other variables, calculated with equation $100(\exp^{\beta}-1)\%$, where β is the estimated regression coefficient for a variable.

4. DISCUSSION

The regression results were all highly significant with p-values essentially 0 (they were all less than 0.000005) and a sample size of 707,634 for 2022 and 707,735 for 2023. The IS_HIGH_FLD_RISKTRUE, IS_BUSINESSTRUE, and IS_HIGH_FLDRISKTRUE: IS_BUSINESSTRUE variables are binary, so their coefficient estimates indicate the degree of the linear relationship between the predictor and the **average** of the response. The first, IS_HIGH_FLD_RISKTRUE indicates if the property is in a high-risk flood area. The coefficient estimates of approximately -0.057 and -0.054 for 2022 and 2023 respectively, indicate that holding other variables constant, there is an associated *decrease* of approximately 0.057 and 0.057 in the log of the property value, or $100(e^{0.057}-1)\% \approx 5.9\%$ in 2022 and $100(e^{0.057}-1)\% \approx 5.5\%$ in 2023 in the property value. So, controlling for the other variables

present in the model, properties classified as higher flood risk appear to have slightly *lower* property values on average for both years.

The negative relationship between flood risk and property values is well-supported in previous studies. Properties located in high flood-risk areas often experience lower market values due to several factors, including increased insurance costs and higher risks of damage. Atreya, Ferreira, and Kriesel (2013) found that flood risk can reduce property values by 4% to 12%, largely due to expensive flood insurance premiums. Similarly, repeated flooding events led to a reduction of about 5% to 10% in property values due to the anticipated repair and maintenance costs (Bin et al., 2008). Market perception also plays a crucial role, as buyers often devalue properties in flood-prone areas out of concern for long-term sustainability (Harrison et al., 2001). These findings justify the 5.5% to 5.9% reduction in property values for properties in high flood-risk areas observed in this study.

The second, IS_BUSINESSTRUE, indicates if a business owns the property. The coefficient estimates of -0.095 and -0.092 for 2022 and 2023 respectively, indicate that holding other variables constant, there is an associated *decrease* of approximately 0.095 and 0.092 in the log of the property value, or approximately 10% and 9.6% in the property value. So, controlling for the other variables present in the model, properties purchased by businesses appear to also have slightly *lower* property values on average for both years. Studies show that businesses are often more price-sensitive and willing to purchase properties with a lower initial value, particularly in high-risk or less desirable locations. According to Eichholtz, Kok, and Quigley (2010), corporate-owned properties often face price suppression due to their investment strategies, which prioritize potential future gains over present market value. Additionally, corporate owners tend to invest in areas where the risk (such as flood risk) is higher, driving property values down (Cheshire & Sheppard, 2002). These factors contribute to the observed 9.6%-10% decrease in property values for business-owned properties in both years.

Further, for the categorical variable SITUS city variable, all cities show a similar percentage decrease in property values, which aligns with studies suggesting that location-specific factors such as zoning regulations, infrastructure quality, and local market conditions consistently affect property values (Glaeser et al., 2005). Certain city locations may experience market depreciation due to less favorable economic or environmental conditions (McDonald & McMillen, 2010). The

range of SITUS coefficients from -0.97 to -2.52 represent significant differences among cities which likely represents differences in location-specific factors.

The positive relationship between business ownership and flood risk on property values, as shown by the coefficient estimates of 0.123 and 0.109 for 2022 and 2023, aligns with research indicating that businesses often invest in higher-risk properties with the potential for long-term profit or redevelopment. Business owners may be more willing to take on properties in high-risk areas because they are better equipped to manage risk through insurance, tax incentives, or the ability to offset potential losses against other gains (Atreya & Ferreira, 2015). Additionally, businesses may purchase these properties with the intention of future redevelopment, which could lead to an increase in the perceived value of the land despite the immediate flood risk (Dehring, Depken, & Ward, 2007). This explains the observed 11.5%-13.1% increase in property values for properties that are both high-risk and business-owned.

The pattern is similar for both years; namely, for both 2022 and 2023, high flood-risk properties tend to have slightly higher property values, business-owned properties slightly lower, and both high flood-risk and business-owned properties are appreciably higher.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this study provide valuable insights into how flood risk and business ownership influence property values in Broward County, Florida. Both high flood-risk properties and business-owned properties were associated with systematic decreases in value, with estimated declines of around 10% and 5.8% respectively in 2022, slightly improving in 2023. This suggests that the market may be progressively adjusting to these risks over time. However, when flood risk and business ownership interact, the data reveals a surprising trend: high flood-risk properties owned by businesses were valued significantly higher, increasing by approximately 13.1% in 2022 and 11.5% in 2023.

This increase may be explained by businesses' ability to manage and mitigate flood risk more effectively than individual homeowners, using resources for flood defenses, insurance, or tax incentives. Additionally, businesses may view high flood-risk properties as strategic investments, particularly if these properties are undervalued due to perceived risk. The decreasing gap from

2022 to 2023 further suggests that market conditions or perceptions around flood risk may be shifting.

While these findings offer compelling evidence that the combination of business ownership and flood risk leads to higher property valuations, further research is needed to explore the causal mechanisms at play. Understanding why and how businesses can capitalize on high flood-risk properties will be essential for future policy development aimed at balancing economic stability with climate resilience.

6. LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations that must be acknowledged. First, the analysis relies on data from Broward County, Florida, limiting the generalizability of the findings to other regions with different flood risk profiles or market conditions. Additionally, while the hedonic pricing model provides valuable insights, it assumes that all relevant factors impacting property values are accounted for, which may not fully capture the complexities of the housing market. Another limitation is the exclusion of certain intangible factors, such as buyer perceptions of flood risk, access to flood insurance, and varying levels of flood risk awareness, which can affect property values but are difficult to quantify. Furthermore, the study focuses solely on property values in 2022 and 2023, making it difficult to capture long-term trends or shifts in market behavior in response to policy changes, such as the new flood disclosure laws. Lastly, the study does not establish a causal relationship between flood risk, business ownership, and property values, leaving room for further investigation into underlying mechanisms driving these patterns.

Possible extensions of this study include further regression analyses, such as partial F-tests, or predictor subset selection which may help uncover the strongest predictors of property value, not only individually, but collectively as a group. Advanced regression techniques to improve model fit would include non-linear modeling, for example, polynomial transformations of the predictor variables. Further, more sophisticated or precise determination of business ownership. For example, verifying a small sample by hand, or creating a hand-verified training set and using a machine learning model to recognize the difference reliably. A recent study showed that recent flooding was not well explained by FEMA flood zones. A later extension of this project may include more accurate flood risk information, for example, annual rainfall or max daily rainfall,

and perhaps at a more geographically fine-grained level, perhaps a city or zip code. Finally, studying other features in this dataset could deepen insight into the research questions and improve the model fit.

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